

Evaluating Smart Classroom Setups For Sustainable Education In Gicumbi District, Rwanda

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ABSTRACT

Smart classrooms integrating digital technologies, interactive tools, and learner-centered pedagogies are increasingly promoted worldwide as a pathway to strengthen teaching, enhance student engagement, and foster 21st-century skills. In Rwanda, substantial investment in smart classrooms across public secondary schools reflects the national ICT in Education Policy and commitment to Sustainable Development Goal 4. Yet provision of technology alone does not guarantee effectiveness. This study evaluated the effectiveness of smart classroom setups in Gicumbi District by focusing on four critical components: technological infrastructure, pedagogical readiness, learning environment, and institutional support. A convergent mixed-methods design was employed, drawing on data from 296 students, 22 teachers, and 5 head teachers. Quantitative data were analyzed using descriptive statistics and correlations, while qualitative insights were explored through thematic analysis. Findings indicate that although most schools have computers (98%) and projectors (95%), only about half are functional or aligned with curricula. Internet reliability is limited (45%), and smart boards are largely non-operational (3%). Student performance (72%) and engagement (mean = 3.7/5; 62% reporting high engagement) remain moderate. Overall, the evaluation demonstrates that smart classrooms in Gicumbi are only partially effective, with their potential constrained by inadequate teacher training, limited technical support, and weak institutional frameworks. Strengthening these dimensions is essential if smart classrooms are to contribute meaningfully to sustainable educational development.

Keywords: Smart Classrooms; ICT In Education; Pedagogical Readiness; Learning Environment

INTRODUCTION

The rapid advancement of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) has profoundly transformed education worldwide, enabling more innovative, interactive, and learner-centered pedagogical practices. Smart classrooms characterized by the integration of digital tools such as computers, projectors, interactive boards, and reliable internet connectivity are widely regarded as a major innovation in technology-enhanced learning [1,2]. When effectively implemented, these environments can enhance student engagement, foster collaboration, promote digital literacy, and strengthen the foundations for sustainable educational development. In recognition of this potential, the Government of Rwanda has made substantial investments in smart classrooms across public secondary schools as part of its ICT in Education Policy and broader development agenda aligned with Sustainable Development Goal 4 [3,4]. However, the provision of infrastructure alone does not guarantee educational transformation. Evidence from Rwanda

and other sub-Saharan African contexts shows that smart classrooms are often underutilized and weakly integrated into teaching practice, particularly in rural districts such as Gicumbi [5,6]. Several systemic constraints undermine their effectiveness. These include insufficient teacher training and limited pedagogical capacity [7], inadequate technical support and maintenance mechanisms [8], a lack of contextualized digital content and curriculum alignment [9], and persistent infrastructural challenges such as unreliable electricity and poor internet connectivity [5]. Furthermore, the absence of a coherent implementation framework has led to fragmented practices, preventing the realization of the full potential of smart classrooms [1,9].

These challenges raise critical questions about whether smart classrooms in Rwanda are achieving their intended purpose of improving learning outcomes and contributing to sustainable educational development. This study therefore goes beyond documenting the presence of ICT resources to

evaluate the *effectiveness* of smart classroom setups in public secondary schools in Gicumbi District. Effectiveness is judged in relation to national ICT in Education Policy targets and Sustainable Development Goal 4, with particular attention to four critical components: technological infrastructure, pedagogical readiness, supportive learning environments, and institutional and policy support. By assessing not only the availability but also the functionality, usability, and pedagogical alignment of smart classroom resources, the study provides evidence-based insights into the extent to which these initiatives contribute to sustainable educational development in Rwanda.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Smart classrooms are increasingly recognized as transformative learning environments that integrate digital technologies, interactive tools, and learner-centered pedagogies. They respond to the growing demand for technology-enhanced education that equips learners with 21st-century competencies such as collaboration, critical thinking, problem-solving, and digital literacy [10]. However, their effectiveness is not guaranteed by the mere provision of devices or internet connectivity; rather, it depends on how well technological, pedagogical, environmental, and institutional components are designed and integrated into everyday teaching and learning practices. Several theoretical perspectives shed light on how smart classrooms function. The Smart Learning Environment Theory emphasizes that technology must be embedded within adaptive and interactive pedagogical contexts to create meaningful and sustainable learning experiences [1]. Similarly, the Digital Learning Environment Theory highlights that digital tools only become transformative when they are aligned with curriculum goals and teaching strategies that support knowledge construction rather than passive transmission [2].

The Community of Inquiry framework further underlines the importance of convergence among cognitive presence, social presence, and teaching presence in ensuring that technology integration leads to genuine improvements in learning [3]. The Flipped Classroom Model also illustrates how restructuring instructional delivery, with content accessed online and classroom time devoted to active engagement, can enhance learner autonomy, collaboration, and self-regulation [4]. Taken together, these frameworks suggest that the value of smart classrooms lies not in the existence of devices, but in their capacity to enrich pedagogy, strengthen interaction, and improve outcomes. Empirical evidence from international studies reinforces this position while also revealing mixed results. Del Hierro [10] identifies structured teacher training, curriculum alignment, and reliable technical support as critical success factors, warning that without them digital resources risk being

underutilized. Xu [11] emphasizes the need for adaptive and inclusive models that cater to diverse learner needs, noting that rigid or poorly contextualized designs can reduce impact. Mounkoro et al. [12] demonstrate that AI-powered platforms and real-time analytics improve engagement where teachers are skilled and supported by their institutions, while Plueger [13] highlights that flexible classroom arrangements and cloud-based resources create opportunities for collaboration and self-paced learning. Alfoudari et al. [14] add that smart classrooms contribute meaningfully to sustainable educational development only when they are embedded within coherent implementation frameworks. These findings underline that technology alone is insufficient; its effectiveness depends on alignment with pedagogy, institutional structures, and contextual realities.

In sub-Saharan Africa, however, studies consistently point to persistent challenges in the implementation of smart classrooms. Common barriers include inadequate infrastructure, unreliable electricity and internet, and low ICT competence among teachers [5,15,16]. In Rwanda, smart classrooms were launched in 2016 under the ICT in Education Policy to advance digital learning and align with Sustainable Development Goal 4. Despite this investment, many rural schools particularly in districts such as Gicumbi still struggle with limited integration of technology into teaching [6,7]. Harris et al. [17] observe that administrative resistance, financial constraints, and weak planning undermine sustainability, while Ngendabanga et al. [8] note that fragmented policy frameworks create inconsistencies in practice. Without continuous professional development, reliable maintenance systems, and strong institutional leadership, the potential of smart classrooms remains constrained despite the government's substantial investment [9].

These insights reveal a clear research gap. While much of the existing literature in Rwanda has focused on the provision of ICT resources, little attention has been paid to their actual functionality, pedagogical alignment, and long-term developmental value. This study therefore evaluates smart classroom setups in Gicumbi District through four critical components—technological infrastructure, pedagogical readiness, learning environment, and institutional support. By focusing not only on availability but also on usability and impact, the study provides evidence-based insights into how smart classrooms contribute to teaching effectiveness, student engagement, collaboration, and critical thinking, and thereby to sustainable educational development.

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a convergent mixed-methods design to evaluate the effectiveness of smart

classroom setups in five public secondary schools in Gicumbi District. The sample comprised 296 students (157 Senior Three and 139 Senior Five), 22 teachers with at least five years of teaching experience, and 5 head teachers, selected purposively to capture participants directly engaged with smart classroom use. Data were collected through structured student questionnaires on infrastructure, equipment functionality, learning environment conditions, engagement, and performance; semi-structured interviews with teachers and head teachers focusing on pedagogical readiness, training, institutional support, and policy clarity; and observation checklists to verify the availability, functionality, and curriculum alignment of ICT resources. Quantitative data were analyzed using descriptive statistics (frequencies, percentages, means, and standard deviations) and Pearson correlation analysis to assess associations between infrastructure, learning environment variables, and reported outcomes. Qualitative data from interviews were analyzed thematically, with illustrative quotes used to contextualize statistical findings. Ethical clearance was obtained from the Research Ethics Committee of Kabale University and the Gicumbi District

Education Office. Participation was voluntary, informed consent was obtained from all adult respondents, and student participation was supported through parental consent and school authorization.

RESULTS

The evaluation of smart classroom setups in Gicumbi District revealed a persistent gap between the availability of digital resources and their effective utilization. As shown in Figure 1, while 98% of classrooms were equipped with computers, only 65% were functional and 60% aligned with curriculum requirements. Projectors were present in 95% of schools, yet fewer than 60% were functional and only half were used in ways that supported teaching objectives. Although internet connectivity was nominally universal (100%), only 45% of connections were reliable and 40% adequately supported integration. Smart boards were the weakest component, with only 10% available, 3% functional, and 1% aligned with curriculum demands. These findings indicate that provision has not translated into effective use, supporting earlier observations that technology without adequate planning risks underutilization [5,9].

Figure 1: Availability, functionality, and curriculum alignment of smart classroom technologies in Gicumbi District.

Source: Field data (2025)

Student evaluations of the learning environment (Figure 2) suggested moderate conditions. Classroom comfort (mean = 3.8/5; 65% positive) and lighting (mean = 4.0/5; 70% positive) were rated relatively high, while seating (mean = 3.5/5; 55% positive) and noise control (mean = 3.2/5; 50% positive) scored considerably lower. Accessibility of learning

materials was moderately strong (mean = 3.9/5; 68% positive). These results suggest that physical and environmental factors constrain the pedagogical potential of smart classrooms, aligning with Plueger’s [13] emphasis on the role of flexible and supportive spaces in enabling collaboration and effective technology use.

Figure 2: Student evaluations of the learning environment in smart classrooms (clustered bar chart).

Source: Field data (2025)

With respect to student outcomes, performance averaged 3.6/5 ($\approx 72\%$ achievement), while engagement was rated 3.7/5, with 62% of students reporting high engagement (Figure 3). These findings indicate moderate benefits but fall short of demonstrating strong effectiveness, reinforcing Xu’s [11] argument that digital technologies require adaptive pedagogy to meaningfully enhance critical thinking and active learning.

Figure 3: Student performance and engagement in smart classrooms (radar chart).
Source: Field data (2025)

To determine the contribution of smart classroom components to outcomes, Pearson correlation analysis was conducted (Table 1). Results showed that technological infrastructure was strongly and positively associated with student outcomes ($r = .62$, $p < .01$), indicating that the presence and functionality of ICT equipment significantly influence performance. The learning environment was also positively correlated ($r = .54$, $p < .05$), highlighting the importance of seating, lighting, and noise control in supporting effective use of technology. These results support Del Hierro’s [10] position that the effectiveness of smart classrooms depends not only on infrastructure but also on conducive learning spaces. The moderate strength of these associations suggests, however, that current setups in Gicumbi are only partially effective and require complementary investments in teacher capacity and institutional support to realize their full potential.

Table 1: Correlation between smart classroom components and student outcomes.

Variables	Technological Infrastructure	Learning Environment	Student Outcomes
Technological Infrastructure	1.00	.55	.62
Learning Environment	.55	1.00	.54
Student Outcomes	.62	.54	1.00

Source: Researcher’s analysis (2025)

Finally, qualitative insights from interviews with teachers and head teachers revealed systemic barriers limiting pedagogical effectiveness. Respondents emphasized the absence of structured ICT training and ongoing professional development, leaving many to rely on traditional methods despite access to digital tools. One head teacher noted: “Many teachers have never received proper ICT training, so they rely on traditional methods even in smart classrooms.” This aligns with Alfoudari et al.’s [14] assertion that teacher readiness is central to effective integration. Participants also reported insufficient policy guidance and sporadic technical support, echoing Ngendabanga et al.’s [8] findings on implementation challenges. Collectively, these insights suggest that without institutional commitment and teacher capacity-building, the effectiveness of smart classrooms remains limited, and their contribution to sustainable educational development cannot yet be considered fully achieved.

DISCUSSION

The findings of this study reveal a persistent mismatch between the provision of smart classroom

infrastructure and its effective pedagogical use. Although computers, projectors, and internet connectivity were widely available in Gicumbi District, their limited functionality and weak curriculum alignment substantially reduced their impact. This confirms the proposition of the Digital Learning Environment Theory, which stresses that technology exerts little influence unless it is systematically integrated into curriculum and instructional practice [2]. The pattern also mirrors earlier observations in Rwanda and other sub-Saharan African contexts, where significant infrastructural investments remain underutilized due to weak pedagogical integration and contextual barriers [5,8].

The study further showed that learning environments were only moderately supportive, with deficiencies in seating arrangements and noise control undermining collaboration and interactivity. In line with the Smart Learning Environment Theory, such environmental conditions are integral to meaningful learning because they shape adaptability, interaction, and engagement [1]. Weak physical conditions in Gicumbi therefore help explain why smart classrooms have not translated into substantial

improvements in teaching and learning despite heavy infrastructural investment. Student performance and engagement were also found to be moderate rather than strong, supporting Xu's [11] assertion that digital technologies require adaptive and innovative pedagogy to yield significant gains in critical thinking and active learning. This outcome resonates with the Community of Inquiry framework, which emphasizes that cognitive, social, and teaching presence must converge for digital environments to be effective [3]. In the Gicumbi context, limited teacher ICT competence and reliance on traditional methods hindered this convergence, thereby reducing the pedagogical value of smart classrooms.

Correlation analysis further confirmed that both technological infrastructure ($r = .62, p < .01$) and the learning environment ($r = .54, p < .05$) were positively associated with student outcomes. These findings affirm Del Hierro's [10] view that both technology and environment are critical determinants of effectiveness. Yet the moderate strength of these relationships indicates that current smart classroom setups are only partially effective. This limitation reflects the absence of complementary factors such as teacher proficiency, institutional commitment, and policy coherence. In line with the Flipped Classroom Model, technology must be accompanied by restructured instructional design and sustained professional development if it is to foster active engagement and deeper learning [4]. Overall, while Rwanda's investment in smart classrooms is consistent with national education priorities and Sustainable Development Goal 4, the initiative has not yet achieved its intended outcomes in Gicumbi District. Sustainable impact requires more than infrastructure: it depends on capacity-building for teachers, clear implementation frameworks, reliable maintenance systems, and supportive leadership.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study concludes that although smart classrooms in Gicumbi District are equipped with foundational technologies such as computers, projectors, and internet connectivity, their potential to transform teaching and learning remains underutilized. The evidence demonstrates that availability alone does not guarantee improved learning outcomes; rather, effectiveness depends on functionality, curriculum alignment, and meaningful pedagogical integration. Persistent challenges including inadequate equipment maintenance, limited teacher competence in ICT integration, and weak institutional support continue to constrain the value of these investments. To address these challenges and align more closely with Rwanda's ICT in Education Policy and the broader objectives of Sustainable Development Goal 4, a comprehensive and multi-pronged strategy is required. First, schools need reliable technical support systems to ensure the functionality and

sustainability of ICT resources. Second, teacher capacity must be strengthened through continuous, practice-oriented professional development that equips educators to embed digital tools into lesson planning and delivery. Third, clear policy frameworks and committed leadership are necessary to guide implementation, resource allocation, and accountability in the use of smart classrooms. Finally, improvements to the physical learning environment including classroom layout, seating, lighting, and noise control are essential to create conditions conducive to collaborative, interactive, and technology-enhanced learning. Taken together, these recommendations highlight that achieving the full promise of smart classrooms in Rwanda requires not only infrastructure but also the integration of pedagogy, institutional support, and enabling environments. Sustainable educational impact will depend on moving beyond provision toward strategic, coordinated, and capacity-driven utilization.

STUDY LIMITATIONS

Although this study provides valuable insights into the effectiveness of smart classrooms in Gicumbi District, several limitations must be acknowledged. First, the geographical scope was restricted to five public secondary schools in one district, which limits the generalizability of the findings to other regions of Rwanda that may differ in socio-economic or infrastructural conditions [5,16]. Second, the study relied primarily on self-reported data from teachers and students. Such data may be subject to response and social desirability biases, potentially obscuring the actual extent of smart classroom utilization [7]. Although the instruments were validated by experts [14], the absence of objective usage records constrained the ability to fully assess whether ICT facilities were consistently and effectively applied in line with the Digital Learning Environment Theory [2]. Third, the cross-sectional design restricted the capacity to establish causal relationships or examine long-term effects, which are essential for understanding the sustainability of smart classroom initiatives and their contribution to Sustainable Development Goal 4 [3]. Future research should therefore employ longitudinal and mixed-method designs, incorporating classroom observations, usage logs, and long-term outcome data. Such approaches would provide stronger evidence of how smart classroom components influence student engagement, pedagogical innovation, and sustainable educational development in Rwanda.

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